

MINDFULNESS AND ITS IMPACT ON HAPPINESS & JOB SATISFACTION: A STUDY OF WORKING PROFESSIONAL

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Abstract

Mindfulness is a state of responsiveness in which people attend to happening events and involvements in a responsive and non-judgmental manner. This research focuses on how mindful and active an employee is at work and what satisfaction is derived from that work or job. Also, this research covers how the mindfulness of a person leads to job satisfaction, which ultimately results in the increased efficiency and productivity of the employee in achieving personal as well as organizational objectives. The study often highlights the relationship between non-judgmental awareness of one's emotions, that is, mindfulness, and an increased level of happiness. Convenient sampling and a structured questionnaire were used to collect primary data. ANOVA and chi-square were used for testing hypotheses. The study revealed that mindfulness has a significant impact on happiness and job satisfaction, while happiness does not have an impact on job satisfaction.

Keywords: Mindfulness, Happiness, Job Satisfaction, Workplace, Attentiveness

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, mindfulness has been the key focus area for a large group of people, including psychologists, researchers, academicians, corporate houses, and many more. Understanding and increasing happiness, mindfulness, and satisfaction among working professionals continue to be important, yet the underrepresented area of research. Happiness refers to a mental or emotional state that encompasses pleasant emotions ranging from contentment to intense delight that is, experiencing pleasure in the context of satisfaction, well-being, good spirit, and welfare.

Mindfulness

Mindfulness is the cognitive ability to be thoroughly present and aware of where and what a person is doing or about to do, and not be overly expressive or overwhelmed by what is going on within as well as in their surroundings. It implies that the mind is fully focused on what are currently happening, what one is doing, and the space one is emotionally drawn to. The mind might take a getaway approach, lose sensation with the body, and pretty soon get absorbed by dominating lines of thoughts about something that may have just occurred or perturbed about the future.

Brown (2003) defines mindfulness as that innate level of consciousness that involves attending to the moment-by-moment experience in a conscious state.

According to Kabat and Zinn (1990), mindfulness is a technique for enkindling a specific level of awareness or attentiveness to present-moment experience.

Intent, awareness, and outlook are the three components that make up the meaning of mindfulness (Shapiro et al., 2006).

According to contemporary psychology, mindfulness has been defined as an approach for enhancing attentiveness and responding diligently to the different mental processes that may lead to emotional distress and or substandard behavior. By bringing awareness to present experiences, identifying, observing, and responding to the dynamicity of thoughts, feelings, and emotions in each moment, and by regulating the force of attention.

Henceforth, leads to a feeling of being alert about the ongoing events and happenings. It is often described as the feeling of being wholly present and alive in the present moment.

Job Satisfaction

People's feelings regarding their employment and other facets of their jobs are referred to as "job satisfaction." It refers to how satisfied (content) or dissatisfied (discontent) they are with their jobs. It is understood as a variable that is based on the attitude and outlook of the person. It is an all- inclusive feeling about the job or an interrelated faction of attitudes about different facets of the job.

Job satisfaction is an elated emotional state that can result from performance or job appraisal in order to achieve or facilitate job values. Job dissatisfaction is the un-pleasurable emotional state, as an outcome of frustration or non-attainment of the job values, or necessitating devaluation during appraisal. Job satisfaction and dissatisfaction are like opposites; one cannot have well without bad, where the former is what one aspires to out of the job and the latter is what one regards as a benefaction. Henceforth, it constitutes conjunction of affirmative or non-affirmative perspectives that people develop around their work.

Along with, people absorbed in any organization bring forward diverse needs, demands, and distinct wisdom, which thereafter induce job expectations, arousing the feeling of satisfaction or dissatisfaction. Job satisfaction represents the extent of the job expectations and whether or not they are matched with the actual awards and rewards.

Davis (1985) linked job satisfaction with the conduct of the people in the organization they work for.

Locke (1976): an enjoyable, pleasant, or positive psychological state, which is an outcome of job appraisal and job experiences, paves the way for job satisfaction.

Job satisfaction is the constellation of psychological, physiological, and environmental occurrences that direct a person to mention that he/she is satisfied with the job truthfully (Hoppock, 1935).

Job satisfaction can be understood as feelings or emotions on the part of individuals towards those work roles with which they are occupied. (Vroom, 1964).

Happiness

Happiness is defined as "the totality of one's anguish." In the same manner, happiness is indeed defined as "the cumulative admiration of the entire life in general." Happiness, in this perspective, is a culmination of living, as opposed to prerequisites for a peaceful life, such as a pleasant, supportive, and good relationship. Happiness is a very nebulous statement that only the individual may experience (Veenhoven, 2008). Happiness is accomplished in a variety of ways, with synonyms like well-being, contentment, standards of living, and life satisfaction, and many more. Henceforth, it is a powerful psychological metaphor that categorizes theories about what it means to be content.

To date, a massive amount of research has been carried out that supports the importance of mindfulness for achieving happiness. In a controlled environment, Ivztan et al. (2016) performed research that assimilated mindfulness with a range of positive aspects that efficaciously led to a significant increase in happiness levels. Significant correlations between attributes metrics of mindfulness and a wide range of happiness indicators have been discovered. Another analysis revealed that mindfulness explicitly stimulates happiness by boosting insight and versatility in the current moment and even enabling reasonably close, points in time, and sensory interaction with life, i.e., without exclusionary opinions Ryan (2003). It has indeed been attributed to multiple forms of psychological disruptions (such as anxiety, anxiousness, and mental anguish), subjective well-being (general happiness), and well-being (self-actualization). Furthermore, people who already have procured these attributes are better equipped with knowledge and skills to organize and fix day-to-day concerns, which encourage and promote healthy thoughts and general happiness (Hollis Walker 2011). Mindfulness has been further equated with coping with stress, facilitating greater emotional intelligence and regulatory oversight, work-life stability, and improved quality of life (Allen & Kiburz 2011). It also boosts affirmative emotions and feelings, which almost always lay the groundwork for overall satisfaction (Fredrickson 2008).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The experience a person undergoes moment by moment, by bringing together a certain quality and level of attention, is described as mindfulness by Kabat-Zinn (1990). Thondup (1996) explains that mindful people are particularly focused on consciousness, with no consideration of the past or future. Mindfulness is non-censorious and non-analytical. Henceforth, mindful people pay attention to what is going on without denouncing, pondering, or adhering to it (Brown, 2007). Mindful people are said to be vigilant, with intensified cognitive ability and an acknowledgment of how to mitigate obstructions (Zeidan, 2010). According to Dane (2011), it does have significant advantages, including optimizing work achievements and performances. Mindfulness not only impacts performance but also helps with enduring satisfaction in the workplace and reduces psychological weariness (Hu and Elsheger, 2013). Job satisfaction is an evaluative judgment of the work situations of individuals (Weiss, 2002). Lama and Cutler (1998) state that happiness can be fostered by consciously emphasizing and selecting a desirable state of mind. Empirical studies have shown evidence that underlines the causal

association between happiness, well-being, and work habits (Cropanzano & Wright 2001). Previous research has shown that providing training for mindfulness to employees will drive a steadily increasing loop of positive emotional impact, which is a cornerstone of happiness and well-being (Garland, 2015). Happiness can be understood as a multidimensional contrive that comprises cognitive and emotional variables (Hills and Argyle, 2001). Happiness can be a synonym for satisfaction that a person can have with life, coinciding with the concept of subjective wellbeing (Veenhoven, 2008). Work for overall fulfillment (Fredrickson 2008).

Objectives of Study

1. To determine the overall impact of mindfulness, happiness and job satisfaction on working professionals.
2. To determine the impact of mindfulness on job satisfaction of working professionals.
3. To determine the impact of happiness on job satisfaction of working professionals.
4. To determine the impact of mindfulness on happiness of working professionals.
5. To determining the difference in the mindfulness, happiness and job satisfaction of working professionals based on demographical variables.

Hypotheses of Study

1. There is overall significant impact of mindfulness, happiness and job satisfaction on working professionals.
2. There is a significant impact of mindfulness on job satisfaction of working professionals.
3. There is a significant impact of happiness on job satisfaction of working professionals.
4. There is a significant impact of mindfulness on happiness of working professionals.
5. There is difference in the mindfulness, happiness and job satisfaction of working professionals based on demographical variables.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey design was used for the present study. The target populations for the study were the working professionals of the state of Uttar Pradesh. Data for the study was collected with the help of a self-structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was prepared and filled out with the help of Google Form. A purposive sampling technique was used in collecting primary data from 150 respondents. This study is based on primary data collected from the study area and secondary data obtained from literature. Data obtained from respondents was analyzed by using descriptive statistics such as frequencies of response, percentages, and hypotheses that have been checked by one-way ANOVA and chi-square. Result & Discussion

The present study is based on primary data, and the respondents are working professionals. Table 1 highlights the demographic profile of respondents where male and female percentages are 47% and 53%, which confirms almost equal representation of them.

Table 1: Demographical Profile

Dimensions		Frequency	Percentage
Marital Status	Married	31	21
	Unmarried	119	79
Gender	Male	71	47
	Female	79	53
Age	21-30	129	86
	31-40	14	9
	41-50	4	3
	More than 50	3	2
Educational Status	Graduation	64	43
	PG	82	54
	Doctorate	4	3
Occupation	Govt.	102	68
	Private	33	22
	Business	15	10
Family Status	Nuclear	85	57
	Joint	65	43

The finding may have an impact on the number of married working professionals (79%). More than 80% of respondents are below the age of 30, which indicates that the present study was more focused on young professionals. According to the data, more than 50% of respondents are post-graduate, compared to 43 percent who are graduates, and only 3% have doctoral degrees. The study covers the working professionals of government employees (68%), private sector employees (22) and business personnel (10). Family status also affects job satisfaction, happiness, and mindfulness of working professionals. The study illustrates that 57% of respondents are from nuclear families and 43% are from joint families.

Objective 1: To determine the overall impact of mindfulness, happiness and job satisfaction on working professionals.

H1: There is overall significant impact of mindfulness, happiness and job satisfaction on working professionals.

Outcomes: The p-value at the significance level was compared to the null hypothesis to determine whether any of the differences between the means of overall impact of mindfulness, happiness, and job satisfaction on working professionals is statistically significant (Table 2).

Table 2: ANOVA Table of Mindfulness, Happiness and Job Satisfaction

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	5224.661	4	1306.165	4.370317	0.002562	2.454213
Within Groups	32875.91	110	298.8719			
Total	38100.57	114				

In this case, the table value (2.45) is less than the calculated value (4.37), so the null hypothesis is rejected and it is concluded that there is an overall significant impact of mindfulness, happiness, and job satisfaction on working professionals.

Objective 2: To determine the impact of mindfulness on job satisfaction of working professionals.

H2: There is a significant impact of mindfulness on job satisfaction of working professionals.

Outcomes: To prove the concerned hypothesis, one-way ANOVA has been used to determine whether any of the differences between the means of mindfulness and job satisfaction experienced by working professionals is statistically significant. The p-value at significance level is compared to the null hypothesis (Table 3).

Table 3: ANOVA Table of Mindfulness and Job Satisfaction

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	6858.589	4	1714.647	6.688460082	9.27E- 05	2.472927
Within Groups	23072.32	90	256.3591			
Total	29930.91	94				

In the particular case where F_{cal} (6.68) is greater than F_{tab} (2.4), we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no statistical difference between the means of mindfulness and job satisfaction. Therefore, there is a significant impact of mindfulness on job satisfaction for working professionals.

Objective 3: To determine the impact of happiness on job satisfaction of working professionals.

H3: There is a significant impact of happiness on job satisfaction of working professionals.

Outcomes: To determine whether any of the differences between the means of happiness and job satisfaction experienced by working professionals is statistically significant, the p-value at the significance level was compared to the null hypothesis (Table 4).

Table 4: ANOVA Table of Happiness & Job Satisfaction

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	1993.777778	4	498.4444	1.064585	0.386653	2.605975
Within Groups	18728.22222	40	468.2056			
Total	20722	44				

The table value (2.60) is greater than the calculated value (1.06), so the null hypothesis is accepted and the difference between the means of happiness and job satisfaction among working professionals is not statistically significant. Therefore, we conclude that there is no significant impact of happiness on job satisfaction.

Objective 4: To determine the impact of mindfulness on happiness of working professionals.

H4: There is a significant impact of mindfulness on happiness of working professionals.

Outcomes: To test the hypothesis, one-way ANOVA was used to see if any of the differences between the means of mindfulness and happiness on working professionals were statistically significant, and the p-value at the significance level was compared to the null hypothesis (Table 5).

Table 5: ANOVA Table of Mindfulness & Happiness

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	10077.84	4	2519.461	14.63696	3.9E-09	2.479015
Within Groups	14631.06	85	172.1301			
Total	24708.9	89				

The above table shows the greater value of F_{cal} than F_{tab} . Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis. It shows no statistical difference between the means of mindfulness and happiness, and we conclude that there is a significant impact of mindfulness on the happiness of working professionals.

Objective 5: To determining the difference in the mindfulness, happiness and job satisfaction of working professionals based on demographical variables.

H5: There is difference in the mindfulness, happiness and job satisfaction of working professionals based on demographical variables.

Outcomes: For the determination of the difference on the basis of demographics, the chi-square test was used. All the dimensions were tested at a 5% level of significance, and according to their values, a null hypothesis may be accepted or rejected (Table 6). While determining the impact of job satisfaction, mindfulness, and happiness on demographical variables of respondents, the study revealed that there was no difference in the level of job

satisfaction on the basis of gender and academic qualification. Males and females have the same level of job satisfaction. The study also shows that it doesn't matter if respondents have a graduate degree, post-graduate degree, or doctoral degree, they have the same level of job satisfaction. But while taking about job satisfaction according to age and marital status, both sets have the same level of job satisfaction. The null hypothesis for happiness and gender was rejected. That shows that males and females have the same level of happiness, and the marital status of respondents also does not show a significant difference in happiness. Mindfulness is the ability to be attentive to what is going on in your surroundings, and the present study found that men and women are different with respect to their mindfulness, but marital status, age, and academic qualification show no significant difference, which means they all have a sense of mindfulness.

Table 6: Chi-Square Table of Mindfulness, Happiness & Job Satisfaction on Demographics of Respondents

Dimension	Degree of Freedom	Calculated Chi-Square Value	Table Chi-Square Value	Null Hypothesis	Result
Job Satisfaction & Gender	4	12.3	9.49	Rejected	No Difference
Job Satisfaction & Marital Status	4	1.9	9.49	Accepted	Difference Exist
Job Satisfaction & Age	12	9.70	21.06	Accepted	Difference Exist
Job Satisfaction Academic Qualification	8	16.95	15.50	Rejected	No Difference
Happiness & Gender	4	12.09	9.49	Rejected	No Difference
Happiness & marital Status	4	13.87	9.49	Rejected	No Difference
Happiness & Age	12	21.02	21.06	Accepted	Difference Exist
Happiness & Academic Qualification	8	7.79	15.50	Accepted	Difference Exist
Mindfulness & Gender	4	7.79	9.49	Accepted	Difference Exist
Mindfulness & Marital Status	4	15.35	9.49	Rejected	No Difference
Mindfulness & Age	12	52.36	21.06	Rejected	No Difference
Mindfulness & Academic Qualification	8	56.84	15.50	Rejected	No Difference

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

The average job stress score of working professionals participating in this study was 150, of which the male and female percentages were 47 and 53%, with a very negligible difference. The maximum sample drawn were people working in government entities (nearly 68%). The difference could be because of the variation between participant groups and the variation in the days on which the data was collected. This factor can be further investigated in other research. Regarding job satisfaction, in our study, the average score showed a significant positive relationship with it with mindfulness. A wide range of factors is likely to be responsible for this. One may be varying levels of job satisfaction between the samples drawn. Current research therefore stresses the importance of mindfulness in increasing job satisfaction among working professionals in different sectors. Regarding job satisfaction and happiness, according to general characteristics, significant differences were found depending on age, educational level, and occupation, and thus there was no significant relationship between the two. Regarding age, the maximum sample drawn was from the age group of 21–30 (almost 86%). However, this contrasts with the idea that mindfulness increases with increasing age. This finding may be due to differences in the characteristics of jobs performed by different age groups. Nonetheless, this issue requires further investigation.

The findings of this study suggested that mindfulness had a significant positive relationship with job satisfaction and happiness, but happiness had no significant impact on job satisfaction. Based on these findings, various types of solutions to increase job satisfaction and happiness should be developed and administered through further research.

The primary goal of the paper was to identify and describe the role and impact of mindfulness in the workplace and study its relationship with job satisfaction and happiness of the employees. Such an objective is often vindicated in the light of the upsurge and popularity of the emerging concept of mindfulness, which is overshadowed by a relative lack of facts and evidence supporting it. (Kelly, 2012; Hansen, 2012). The study shows a significant positive relationship between mindfulness, happiness, and job satisfaction among working professionals. For future research, it is recommended that a study with a long-term experimental design, which would assess changes in the level of job satisfaction and happiness of participants and their level of mindfulness, be conducted, taking into consideration a relatively larger sample base for effective generalization. We also recommend measuring mindfulness using various other objective and subjective variables other than satisfaction and happiness. It would be meaningful to simultaneously use self-reports of workers' performance and objectively successful performance criteria to analyze, at different age levels, how they are differently impacted by mindfulness. The study recommended that individuals should practice meditation, yoga, and proper time management to aid in the improvement of their mindfulness. It should also help in the maintenance of better interpersonal relationships and reduce stress. To improve the focus of employees, organizations should use effective employee engagement programs. It is also recommended to appoint a practitioner to help employees with the development of mindful habits and regular support. Long working hours also adversely affect mindfulness, so it is suggested that organizations introduce regular breaks during work hours to maintain and improve the productivity of employees. It also suggested that consistent and various further studies on it as a solution should be conducted for continuous development and improvement in the working capacity of the working professionals.

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